

ISSN:2814-063X

BASUG LAW JOURNAL

BASUG

LAW JOURNAL

Volume 2 | Issue 3
September, 2024

**A Publication of:
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University**

VOL. 2, ISSUE 3, 2024

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2024**

BASUG Law Journal Volume 2 Issue 3 2024

Published by:

Faculty of Law,

Sa'adu Zungur University (formerly Bauchi State University)

For more information, see: www.basuglawjournal.com

To order:

Faculty of Law,

Bauchi State University, Gadau

No: 65, Kano-Kari Road,

Misau,

Bauchi State.

ISSN: 2814-063X

THIS JOURNAL SHOULD BE CITED AS BASUGLJ Volume 2 No 3 2024

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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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THE UTILITY OF WASIYYA UNDER NIGERIAN CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY

By
Alhaji Ahmed Rufai*

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13948285

ABSTRACT

Wasiyya, also known as a will or testament, is an Islamic legal instrument that allows a Muslim to bequeath a portion of their property to their others upon their death. It is a voluntary act that is considered a meritorious deed in Islam. However, wasiyya is subject to certain restrictions and limitations to ensure that it aligns with Islamic principles of justice and fairness. This paper delves into an overview of wasiyya under Islamic law. It examines the meaning, historical background and essential elements of a valid wasiyya, including the roles of management of wasiyya. In conclusion, wasiyya serves as a valuable tool for Muslims to arrange their affairs after their death. However, understanding the concept of wasiyya, is crucial to ensure that it is exercised in accordance with Islamic principles and promotes justice and fairness among heirs and beneficiaries.

Keyword: *Wasiyya, Nigeria, Islamic Law, Death, Will*

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Wasiyyah is an Arabic word which means bequests, will, and legally it is the confirmation of a right of property to some person that takes effect after the death of the testator (Al-Musi).¹

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¹ Qadri Ahmad. Islamic Jurisprudence in the Modern World, (Muhammad Ashraf Publishers Lahore, Pakistan 1923) .pg.16

Before the advent of Islam, Arabs used to make unlimited bequest in favour of any person according to their own interest. Thus, a testator may bequeath a portion or whole of his property to any individual as he desires, relatives and non-relatives inclusive and a times animals or slaves are bequeathed as witnessed in the western world.²

Consequently, in the early days of Islam, the Holy Qur'an enjoined the Muslims to make Wasiyyah to the parents or other relatives. The provision is as follows:

"It is prescribed for you, when death approaches any of you, if he leaves wealth, that he makes a bequest to parents and next of kin, according to reasonable manners. (This is) a duty upon Al-Muttaqin (the pious). Then whoever changes it after hearing it, the sin shall be on those who make the change. Truly, Allah is All-Hearer, All-Knower. But he who fears from a testator some unjust acts or wrongdoings, and thereupon he makes peace between the parties concerned, there shall be no sin on him. Certainly, Allah is Oft-Forgiving, Most Merciful".³

Also in another verse of the Holy Qur'an, it provides:

"And those of you who die and leave behind wives should bequeath for their wives a year's maintenance and residence without turning them out. But if they (the wives) leave, there is no sin on you for that which they do of themselves, provided it is in honourable (e.g lawful marriage). And Allah is All-Mighty, All-Wise".⁴

This order concerning Wasiyyah continued until verse 11 and 12 of Surah Al-Nisa were revealed, where the making of Wasiyyah in favour of parents, legal heirs and widows has been abrogated. As it is mentioned in the Hadith of the Holy Prophet (SAW) that:

"Allah has given everybody having right, his right. So there should be no Wasiyyah for an heir".⁵

² Ibid

³ Q2:180

⁴ Q2:240

⁵ Malik.Anas. *Muwatta* Malik, (Dar-al-Fikr Publishers, cairo, Egypt. 1968). Pg 118

Also it is reported by Ibn Abbas, that Holy Prophet (SAW) said, "*Wasiyyah is not lawful for an heir, unless the other heirs given consent*"⁶

Ibn Abu Hatim reported that Ibn Abbas said about what Allah said as follows: The widow used to reside, and have her provisions provided for her for a year, in her deceased husband's house. Later, the Ayah that specified the inheritance (4:12) abrogated this Ayah (2:240), and thus the widow inherits one-fourth or one-eighth of what her deceased husband leaves behind.⁷

Therefore, if any testator made a Wasiyyah in favour of his legal heir, it can be determined after his death, after the consent of other heirs, if they approved that Wasiyyah, it will be valid, and otherwise it will become invalid. Both ancient and early practices were abrogated with the law of inheritance and it remained for those who are not entitled to the right of inheritance.⁸

Wasiyyah could summarily be seen as an outstanding directive pre-arranged by a person in respect of certain outstanding duties against him, which he/she overtly or covertly did not carry out before his/her death. It may be an order that a debt he owed be paid to his creditor or the outstanding zakat against his wealth be deducted from his estate or Hajj promised before his/her death be performed. It may also be that a property entrusted to him is handed over to the rightful owner(s) or a portion of the property he left behind be utilized for charitable deeds in favour of an individual or organization...

It is worth noting that there are various definitions of Wasiyyah in the context of Islam and these definitions make it known that Wasiyyah can be used in different versions of application. Al-Wasiyyah or Will in Islamic terminology is all instructions a person leaves for tasks to be carried out after his death in accordance to the laws of Islam. In Islamic law, it is a great gift for mankind in cash or debt, and what the person wish to benefited after the death of the owner. This shows the differences between Hibah and Wasiyyah, Hibah is a gift of any items in quality and quantity determined and executed

⁶ Ibid

⁷ Muhammad, M. "*Wasiyyah in Islam*", (Sadaqatu Tayyibatun Foundation, Minna Nigeria, 2012). Pg 12

⁸ Ibid

by the owner before his death, while Wasiyyah is executed after the demise of the possessor.

Wasiyya and Inheritance are only executed after the death of the giver. Islam is much more than a religion; it is a way of life. Islam is a guidance from God that directs us through life, and God willing into the next life. It is for this reason that God also guides us through the process of death and dying. Death will come to each and every one of us; however there are things we can do to make our passing easier for those we leave behind. One of those things is to make sure we leave an Islamically sound will, thus there is compelling evidence that every sane adult Muslim should have a will.⁹

In Islamic law, a wasiyya refers to a will or testamentary disposition made by a Muslim individual to distribute of his property or assets after their death. It is a legal instrument that allows a person (the testator) to specify how their property should be divided among heirs or beneficiaries. The wasiyya is considered a voluntary act of the testator and can be made in addition to the Islamic rules of inheritance outlined in the Quran.¹⁰

Islam is not merely a religion; rather, it is a religion of law that extends over the entire spectrum of human beings and regulates the affairs of its adherents during their lives and even after their life spans on earth, which is commonly known as sharī'ah.. It consists of a creed or doctrine, and a system of perfect rules and regulations which not only tells us how to manage all activities of life in a sound and ethical way but also keeps away from the confusion of any type due to its logical and rational nature. Islamic teachings also provide clear guidance, wisdom, and virtues; and taken altogether they are a perfect guide to mankind of all ages, generations, races, and social strata.. This is the reason why Islamic law is lived in the context of many different cultures throughout the world.¹¹

1.2 HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF WASIYYA UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

In pre-Islamic Arabia an Arab owner had an absolute and almost unlimited power of disposing of his property. He could make the bequest in favor of anyone he chose, he

⁹ Abu Zuhrah, *Sharh qanun al-wasiyyah*, (Dar al-Fikr al-Arabi Publishers, Cairo, 1988) p.11

¹⁰ Ibid

¹¹ Abu Zuhrah, opcit pg 1

was also at liberty to give preference to one heir to the exclusion of other heirs and there was nothing to prevent him from giving away his entire property to some rich stranger, leaving his own children, parents, and kindred in want, which is undesirable in Islamic law.¹²

The Islamic prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) introduced a number of reforms to the law of inheritance, including the establishment of specific shares for certain categories of heirs. However, he also recognized the importance of allowing people to make bequests, and he stipulated that such bequests should not exceed one-third of the testator's estate.¹³

In the tribal society of pre-Islamic Arabia, all female relative lies outside the structure of tribal ties and responsibilities. All hereditary rights were denied to a woman because to become an heir it is necessary to be able to use the javelin, defend oneself from enemies, and command a foraging party. Therefore, it devolved on his male heirs capable of bearing arms, with all female members, i.e., daughters, wives, sisters, mother, and minors being excluded under prevailing social practice. Thus those who inherited the estate in the pre-Islamic system were able to trace their relationship with the propositus by male links exclusively.

According to Islamic context, human being is a trustee of the assets/wealth that he/she owns for the duration of his/her life. Islamic law of will recognizes human being as a trustee of the wealth they owns for the duration of his wealth. When his/her term of life expires, his/her trusteeship over his/her wealth and property expires. It has then to be redistributed in accordance with the directive of the Absolute Owner, i.e., Allāh. The Qurā'n says:

"To Allah belongs the heritage of the heavens and the earth".¹⁴

Therefore, the right to own property should be exercised within the confines set by Allāh. Ibn Ahmed Olgar succinctly writes in this regard:

"If we fully understand that wealth is a trust (amānah) given to us by Allāh and Allāh is testing us to see how we will discharge the wealth,

¹² Muhammad, M.I. *Wasiyyah in Islam*, (Sadaqatu Tayyibatun Foundation, Minna Nigeria, 2012) p.56

¹³ Ibid

¹⁴ Q3:180

this would be the stepping stone to us using our wealth in accordance with the commandments of Allāh and attaining felicity (al-jannah).¹⁵

While commenting on the above quoted verse, Yūsuf ‘Alī submits that:

“Material wealth or property is only called ours during our short life here. So all gifts are ours in trust only; they ultimately revert to Allah, to whom belongs all that is in the heavens or on the earth.”¹⁶

Therefore, it is ethically incumbent upon a Muslim to make moral exhortations and give spiritual directions to his/her close relatives that what should be done regarding his property after his/her demise.

Making a will enable a person to address exceptional conditions of merit or demerit, of need of affluence, known only to the testator or testatrix. The concept of will in Islam safeguards against a breach of ties among the kindred and is intended to prevent the showing of favouritism to any heir to the prejudice of the others.¹⁷ The noble prophet said:

A man or woman may devoutly worship Allāh for sixty years. Yet when death approaches (one) of them, they act wrongfully (by allocating shares contrary to the stipulation of the Qurā’n) hence the fire becomes binding upon them.¹⁸

For instance Islamic law gives to the mother the right of guardianship, care, and education of her children, the authority of the father and the power of the mother are coexistent and testamentary guardianship, in which the father confers in his will, and it is an emanation of the power of paternal guardianship.¹⁹

At the same time Islamic law has not given unlimited testamentary powers rather restrictions are placed on the power to make a will. The reforms of Islamic law as to these customs has an immense importance. Sharī’ah will serve to explain many of the

¹⁵ Ahmed O. *Fiqhus Sunnah*, (Vol 2. Dar-al- Fikr Publishers, Beirut, Lebanon, 1983) p. 12

⁹ Abdullah Yusuf Ali, *The Meaning of the Holy Qurā’n*, (Cairo, Egypt). p.151.

¹⁷ Sultan, U. *Salah al-Din, al-Mirath wal Wasiyyah bayna al-Shariah wal Qanun*, (sultan publishing USA 2006) p.24

¹⁸ Sunan Abū Dāwūd, ḥadīth no. 2861.

¹⁹ Ibid

modes of transfer of property from one person to another. One of the ways is a testamentary gift, which is highly recommended. Islamic law of a will ensures security to surviving dependents and relatives bound to the deceased by the mutual ties and responsibilities which stem from affinity and blood relationship. In a word the Arabian woman acquires by Islamic law reform a real personality with very important rights which for a long period were denied to her.

1.3 DEFINITION OF WASIYYA (WILL)

The Arabic word for 'Will' is Wasiyyah, which is derived from the root-word 'wasa' meaning 'Gift'. The Testator of a will is called Al-musi in Arabic; and the recipient on the other hand is referred to as Al-Musa lahu. The property or article of bequest is called Al-musa bihi in Arabic. 'Will' is the act of bequeathing a property by its owner to another at the death of the former.²⁰

In other words, Wasiyyah in Islam is the declaration a person makes while alive regarding their property and the arrangements according to Islamic law to be carried out after their death.²¹

Furthermore, a bequest (WasIyya) or will is defined as a transfer to come into operation after the testator's death. The testator is called *Musi*, and the legatee or devisee is called *Musa lahu*, and the executor is called *Wasi*.²²

In Islam, a will must be made by the person while they are alive. A will is made for the purposes of arranging ones property and assets, after their death, for the benefit of others or for charitable purposes.²³

It is the duty of a Muslim who has anything to bequeath not to let two nights pass without writing a will about it."²⁴

²⁰ Kamali, M.H *Principles of Islamic Jurisprudence*, (Islamic Society Publishers, Cambridge, London. 1991) p.24

²¹ Ibid

²² Muhammad, M.0pcit pg 32.

²³ Ibid

²⁴ Sahih bukhari (Volume 3, Book 37, Number 495)

Therefore, wasiyyah could summarily be seen as an outstanding directive pre-arranged by a person in respect of certain outstanding duties against him, which he or she overtly or covertly did not carry out before his/her death. It may be an order that a debt he owed be paid to his creditor or the zakāh outstanding against his wealth be deducted from his estate or ḥajj promised before his/her death be performed. It may also be that a property entrusted to him be handed over to the rightful owner(s) or a portion of the property he left behind be utilized for charitable deeds in favour of an individual or organization.

1.4 ESSENTIAL ELEMENTS OF WASIYYAH

Before a bequest or Wasiyya becomes valid under Islamic law, it must fulfill all these requirements.

1.4.1 TESTATOR (*AL-MUSI*)

There are several conditions to be fulfilled in order to be a testator. Every Muslim who have reached the age of puberty with sound mind or reasoning ability will be given the legal power to make a will. The conditions for a valid wasiyyah stipulates that the testator (*musi*) must be sane, mature, a freeborn (i.e. not a slave), and must have the ability to differentiate between what is good and bad. The provisions of the bequest of an under-aged (not mature) but sane child would be implemented as long as the provisions contained in the wasiyyah are meaningful and useful.²⁵

Before a Wasiyya is valid, the ownership of the property must not be in doubt. The ownership must be devoid of encumbrance. It must have been acquired through lawful means in the first instance by the testator. The testator must also be an adult, sane, and have full right to dispose his property.

Therefore, a minor, a slave, and an insane person cannot be a testator. This is because their property is supposed to be under the care of sane and reliable people who could manage it for them effectively. In Islamic law, a woman can give out her property as *waqf*. But it should not be more than 1/3 of her property. If it will be more than that,

²⁵ Muhammad, M.I “ opcit p. 84

her husband must consent to it. The testator has every right to appoint an agent (*mutawalli*) who is going to manage the affairs of the *waqf*. He has the right to give conditions for the operation of the *waqf*. He may give the agent the sharing formula for the proceeds from the *waqf* for the benefit of people.²⁶

1.4.2 BENEFICIARY (*AL-MUSI LAHU*)

A beneficiary or legatee is someone or something which the will is made. In order for the bequest to be valid and thus, enforceable, the legatee must have existed at the time when the testator died, have the capacity or rights of the ownership of the bequest. The will can be made to the schools, hospitals and others provided that such is not made to any illegal or unlawful activities which are harmful.²⁷

In the case where the bequest has not been accepted or rejected by the legatee and the legatee later dies, the bequest will be considered to be part of his estate in the view of Hanafi on the ground that the bequest will be presumed to have been accepted by the legatee as there is no rejection. In the view of Shafi'i, Maliki, and Hanbali, the heir of the beneficiary will be given the right of acceptance or rejection of the bequest. According to Hanafi, Shafi'i, Maliki, and Hanbali, the permission of the other heirs must be obtained in order to render the will made to an heir to be valid.²⁸

However, according to Imamiyyah, the validity of the will made to an heir will not be affected by the permission of the other heirs, provided that the will must not exceed one third of the estate.²⁹

It has been agreed by all the jurists from different schools that a *dhimmi*, who is not a Muslim but lives in the Muslim lands under the government of Shariah Law, is allowed to make a will to a *dhimmi* or a Muslim, and a Muslim is also allowed to make a will to a *dhimmi* as Allah stated in Quran:

“Allah does not forbid you from those who do not fight you because of religion and do not expel you from your homes from being righteous toward them and acting justly toward them. Indeed, Allah loves those

²⁶ Doi, I.A. *Shari'ah: The Islamic Law* 7th Edition Al-Yassar Publishers, Kano, Nigeria. 2007 p. 44

²⁷ *Ibid*

²⁸ Abu Zuhrah, *opcit.* p. 65

²⁹ *Ibid*

who act justly. Allah only forbids you from those who fight you because of religion and expel you from your homes and aid in your expulsion, forbids that you make allies of them. And whoever makes allies of them, and then it is those who are the wrongdoers.”³⁰

1.4.3 SUBJECT MATTER (AL-MUSIBI HI)

The willed properties which are under the possession of the testator or in possession when the testator dies are transferable after the testator's death. The subject-matter, i.e, the property must not include unlawful things in Islam. It is forbidden for a Muslim to acquire or use the waqf things that the Sharīah has declared haram. The property must be owned. Its owner must be clear and not in doubt. There should be no encumbrance or right attached to the property if someone should give a building that has been used for mortgages; such a waqf is null and void. This is because the rights of creditors are linked to the mortgaged property which can be disposed of so as to recoup their money.³¹

The schools concur that it is necessary that the bequest be capable of being owned, such as property, a house and the benefits ensuing from them. Therefore, the bequest of a thing which cannot be owned customarily (e.g. insects) or legally (e.g. wine, where the testator is a Muslim) is not valid, because transfer of ownership is implicit in the concept of bequest, and when it is not present there remains no subject for the bequest.³²

1.4.4 FORMULA (SIGHA)

This is the instrument or the means by which an endowment is made. An endowment may be made in a number of ways such as by speech and by writing. If it is made by speech, it is in order because words are considered to be the basis of all kinds of expression. It can be said in a number of ways that could not raise doubt. It may be said thus:

³⁰ Q 60:8-9

³¹ Al- Juzairi A. *Al-Fiqh ala Mazahibul Arba'a* ,(Cairo, Egypt. 1969) p. 77

³² Ibid

“I have given this property as waqf in the way of Allah”.³³

It may be written down according to Quran 2:282. There is no fixed format. But what is important is that it should not leave a doubt in the minds of the beneficiaries.³⁴

Sighah may be either clear (*sarih*) or vague (*kinayah*), in verbal or written form. If the will is accepted or rejected when the testator is still alive, the acceptance or rejection will be deemed invalid as it must only be accepted after the testator dies. The testator is allowed to add terms in his will provided that the terms are not contrary to the Islamic teaching. If the will made by the testator in favour of a person and the person dies before the death of the testator without accepting or rejecting the will, the heir of the person will be given the right of acceptance or rejection of the will.³⁵

1.5 THE ROLES OF MANAGEMENT OF WASIYYA

Wasiyya, or Islamic will, is a religious obligation in Islam that allows a person to distribute their assets after their death. The management of wasiyya is the process of ensuring that the wishes of the testator are carried out. Management of Wasiyya can also be referred to as the agents that are in charge of the operation of the *waqf*. *Mutawalli* (agent) has to follow the instruction of the *wāqif*. The property should be managed based on the rules and regulations laid down by the *wāqif* (the testator). *Mutawalli* should not be a minor nor an insane person. He should not be a person under interdiction. He must be competent to carry out the assignment i.e., he should possess the capacity to carry the work. He should be honest and pious. He should also know that he is holding the property on behalf of the testator, and that he is answerable to him in this world and to Allah on the Day of Judgement. He should exercise due care and skill. He should not allow a conflict of interest to arise i.e. he is not allowed to keep for himself proceeds of the *waqf* that are not part of his salary or to make use of the property in a wrong way.³⁶

The roles of management of wasiyya include:

³³ Al-Qairawani, M. *Ar-Risala*. (Al-Huda Huda Publishing Co, Zaria, Nigeria. 1990) p. 34

³⁴ Ibid

³⁵ Al-Raysuni, A. *Nazariyyatul maqasid indal Imam al-Shatibi* (4th ed.. Herndon, Virginia, USA: International Institute of Islamic Thought. 1995) p.10

³⁶ Ibn Qudamah *Al-Mughni*, (vol. 6, Maktabatul Riyadh, Saudi Arabia) P. 292

- a. Determining the validity of the will: The first step in managing a wasiyya is to determine whether the will is valid. This involves ensuring that the testator was of sound mind when he or she made the will, that they were not coerced into making the will, and that the will was executed in accordance with Islamic law.
- b. Identifying the beneficiaries of the will. Once the validity of the will has been established, the next step is to identify the beneficiaries of the will. The beneficiaries are the people who will receive the assets that are bequeathed in the will.
- c. Distributing the assets of the will. The final step in managing a wasiyya is to distribute the assets of the will to the beneficiaries. This is done in accordance with the instructions of the testator.

The agency of *waqf* can be terminated by *wāqif* through mutual agreement, unilateral termination, destruction of the subject matter, loss of legal capacity and death.³⁷

1.6 CONCLUSION

Allah has provided for His creatures what is sufficient for them to live a comfortable life. The rich have been admonished by Islam to share their wealth with the poor. While general charity is good, *waqfs* better as it provides sustainable inflow of resources for the purpose of the *waqf*. A society can flourish when its members do not spend all their wealth on the satisfaction of their own desires but reserve a portion of it for others particularly the underprivileged and the general good of the society. *Waqf* is one of the ways by which this can be done.

The Islamic legal tradition has developed a number of detailed rules governing the making of wills. These rules cover such matters as the capacity of the testator, the form of the will, and the types of property that can be bequeathed.

Wasiyya is an important concept in Islamic law, and it plays a vital role in ensuring that the property of a deceased person is distributed in a fair and equitable manner. It also allows people to express their wishes about how their property should be disposed of after their death.

³⁷ Ibid P. 293

In addition to the aforementioned essential requirements, there are a number of other conditions that must be met for a Wasiyyah to be valid. For example, the bequest must be made freely and voluntarily, and it must not be made in order to defraud the heirs.

If a Wasiyyah does not meet all of the essential requirements, it will be considered invalid. In this case, the bequest will not be honored and the property will be distributed according to the Islamic inheritance rules

The manager of a wasiyya must be a trustworthy and responsible individual who is committed to carrying out the wishes of the testator. He must also have a good understanding of Islamic law and financial matters.